
To Assess the Teaching Competency Between In-service and Pre-service B.Ed. Teacher – Trainees, Affiliated to Bodoland University

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ABSTRACT

Teaching competency is the capacity of a teacher to perform a certain task at a high degree of excellence using their knowledge, abilities, attitude, and experience. It is the most effective technique of teaching the teacher-trainees information, application, and skill units. Currently, it is critical that all teachers be competent. The researcher has attempted to investigate Teaching Competency among the B.Ed. teacher-trainees through the study. The main objectives of the study are to find out the level of teaching competency between In-service and Pre-service B.Ed. teacher-trainees. The methodology used in this study is descriptive study method. In conclusion we can say both In-service and Pre-Service teacher trainees is required for maintaining the quality of education.

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Introduction:

Education is a formal or informal practice that contributes to the development of a person's potential, including their skills, attitudes, behaviours, and values. In this scenario, teachers have a greater role in developing students' character, especially their intellectual character. Knowledge gained through education and its practical applications are always necessary for a country's growth. Effective

instructional techniques that are identity-oriented and have great potential are the foundation of any successful education system or teacher. Teachers have the power to shape and Mold students into decent citizens. They should cultivate a better outlook on the teaching profession, excel in their academic work, and improve lifelong skills in preparation for the future.

In competency-based teacher education program, competency is a necessity that enhance the values, knowledge, and skills that aspiring teachers must demonstrate in order to complete a teacher preparation program.

Statement of the problem

Objectives of the study:

i) To find out the level of teaching competency between In-service and Pre-service B.Ed. teacher-trainees.

Significance of the study:

Teacher training is important because it will help to prepare highly competent teachers to the needs of the 21st century in the context of India and globalization, concerning teaching competency. The study will contribute to the field of research on B.Ed. teacher education programme and reveal the prevailing competency levels of B.Ed. teacher-trainees. This information gained from the study will enhance better approaches and methods for the teachers to promote students' understanding and involvement in creative teaching. Furthermore, it will assist the investigator to learn about the teaching competencies.

Review of related literature:

At the start of any study, a literature review is required to familiarize yourself with the present state of knowledge on the topic, to make sure we are not just repeating what others have already done, to identify gaps in knowledge.

Ponmozhi, (2017) has conducted to assess the teaching proficiency of student teachers in Tamil Nadu. Using a random sampling method, 622 student teachers were chosen from different colleges of education throughout the state. The normative survey approach was employed. The goal of this study is to determine the degree of teaching competence among student instructors. The majority of student teachers' Teaching Competency was found to be average in this study.

Balasubramaniam, (2019) the researcher in his study "Teaching competency of student teachers at B. Ed. level" discovered that teacher trainees have an average level of teaching competency.

Barman & Paramanik, (2019) The researchers have attempted to investigate the "Status of Teacher Competency among the B. Ed. Trainee Teachers" through the study. According to the study's main results, the percentage of B. Ed. teacher trainees who teach in various secondary schools demonstrate a statistically high level of teacher competence.

Sridevi, (2019) has carried out research on the proficiency of teacher trainees. The purpose of the research was to determine the instructional proficiency of future instructors. The majority of the teacher trainees may be seen to have an average level of teaching proficiency.

Methods of the study:

This study demands Descriptive Survey Method to fulfil the basic requirements So, the investigator has adopted the Descriptive Survey Method to carry out the work.

Research Design

Population of the study:

The population of the present study include all the seven (7) B.Ed./DIET Institutions affiliated under Bodoland University during the academic session 2024-2025.

Sample of the study:

The sample of the present study is taken 507 teacher -trainees out of 550 population.

Tools to be used:

Structure Standardized research tool was collected with the help of General Teaching Competency Scale by B.K Passi.

Procedure of data collection:

After the selection of suitable research tool, the next step was the collection of data and the data were collected from selected sample group of B.Ed. teacher-trainees. The investigator approached the principals of the institutions before collection of data. At First, the investigator explained the aim and purpose of the study and then administered the tool to prospective teachers. The teacher- trainees was

encouraged to give correct information and it will be assured that these are to be used only for research purpose and will remain confidential. At the time of data collection, it will be checked that they have answered all the statement.

Delimitation:

The study will be delimited to the B.Ed. teacher-trainees teaching competency of In-service and Pre-service only.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Table 1 :Shows the Percentage of Teaching Competency and Skill Level among B.Ed. Teacher-Trainees of B.Ed. Colleges and DIETs affiliated to Bodoland University based on service

Sl. No.	Sample (n)	Teaching Competency And Skill Level	Range of z-score	Range of raw score	Frequency			
					Pre-Service	%	In-Service	%
1.	507	Superior	+2.01 and above	125 Above	76	18.95	24	22.64
2.		High	+1.26 to +2.00	114-124	76	18.95	25	23.58
3.		Above average	+0.51 to +1.25	103-113	73	18.20	18	16.98
4.		Average/ Moderate	-0.50 to +0.50	89-102	75	18.70	24	22.64
5.		Below Average	-1.25 to -0.51	78-88	34	8.48	8	7.55
6.		Low	-2.00 to -1.26	67-77	26	6.48	3	2.83
7		Inferior	-2.01 and below	0-66	41	10.22	4	3.77
		TOTAL			401	100.0	106	100.00

					0		

The following graphical representation shows the teaching competency and skill level of B.Ed. teacher trainees.

The table 1 and Fig. 1 show the range of Z scores for grade and percentage of Pre-Service and In-Service B.Ed. Teacher-Trainees at different levels of teaching competency skills. From the above given table for the Pre-Service B.Ed. Teacher- Trainees, the maximum number of the samples falls within a standardized z-score range of +1.26 to +2.00 and +2.01 and above which is Grade B and A in the standardized z-score norms indicating “High” and “Superior” level of competency skills. Whereas, for In-Service B.Ed. Teacher-Trainees, maximum number of samples falls within a standardized z-score range of +1.26 to +2.00 which is Grade B in the standardized z-score norms indicating “High” level of competency. Comparing both the values it is revealed that the percentage of In-Service (22.64%) is more “superior” in level of competency than Pre-Service B.Ed. Teacher- Trainees (18.95%). Also, Pre-

Service B.Ed. Teacher- Trainees (10.22%) has more “Inferior” level of competency than In-Service (3.77%). Thus, we can analysis that In-Service B.Ed. Teacher- Trainees are more competent skill than Pre-Service Teacher-Trainees.

Conclusion:

In conclusion we can say that Teacher training program is indeed very crucial for assessing and improving the education quality. It enables the teacher-trainees to develop their teaching competency skills, stay updated with their best practices and enhance with the learner’s outcome. In-service teacher-trainees are experienced teachers with all the practical experienced knowledge improving with the existing skills and adapting with the new knowledge and methods of teaching. Pré-Service teacher-trainees are the new profession, developing their foundational skills of knowledge learning the pedagogical techniques and the management of classroom. Both Pre-Service and In-Service teacher-trainees are essential for developing their effective teaching competency skills.

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